

Stanford University Libraries & Academic Information Resources

INTERNATIONAL DIGITAL LIBRARY R&D MEETING

Green Library, Stanford University
November 29 – December 1, 2009

DRAFT PROCESS AGENDA

Goals & Outcomes

COLLABORATION & COORDINATION will be emphasized throughout the meeting. It is good to hear reports of what individual institutions are doing, but our chief goal in this meeting is to seek opportunities to increase the value of our efforts by collaborating across institutions and coordinating our efforts to get maximum return on collective investments.

We want to leave the meeting with an understanding of the basis for collaboration and/or coordination-- who is willing to commit to collaboration and/or coordination, on what items, and how those relationships might work.

NOV. 28th

Casual dinner for early arrivals at Mike Keller's home

- 5:45 pm** Shuttle departs Sheraton Palo Alto for Mike Keller's home
Shuttle will make two trips, with second trip at approximately 6:00
- 6:00 pm** **Dinner**
- 8:30 pm** Shuttle departs Mike Keller's house for Sheraton Palo Alto
Shuttle will make additional trips as needed

NOV. 29th

Opening Dinner

Menlo Circus Club

190 Park Ln
Atherton, CA 94027

- 4:45 pm** **Shuttle departs Sheraton Palo Alto for Circus Club**
Shuttle will make additional trips as needed
- 5:00 pm** **Reception and Welcome Dinner**
As participants enter the reception area of the Menlo Circus Club they will be invited to "sign in" on a wall chart titled "International Digital Libraries R&D Group". Facilitators, (Andrea Saveri and Eris Weaver) will be positioned there with markers and large post-it notes to assist participants

The names of participating institutions will be listed on the border of the chart. Participants will be invited to write on the chart their ideas for the key attributes of future digital libraries, such as “openness”, “interoperability”, “ease of use”, “device independent”, “trusted”, etc. We will use this chart to do introductions Monday morning.

8:00 pm Shuttle departs Circus Club for Sheraton Palo Alto
Shuttle will make additional trips as needed

NOV. 30th
First Working Day

Bender Room, Green Library
Stanford University

8:20 & 8:40 am Shuttles depart Sheraton Palo Alto

8:30 am Breakfast Buffet in Bender Room

9:00 am Welcome & Orientation

Mike Keller and Chuck Henry welcome the group
Mike Keller introduces facilitators
Facilitators review process/agenda for the two days

9:30 am Introductions & Contributions

Facilitators start the meeting with a brief (5 mins) review of the attributes of the future digital library that were posted the prior evening

Each participant introduces himself with their name, institution, and a BRIEF PHRASE indicating the gift/talent/resource/knowledge they are bringing to the table. These can be concrete (a particular skill) or aspirational (passion, collaborative spirit)

10:15 am Landscape of Current R&D Activities

A tour of the wall chart graphic that was created from the participants' pre-work. This chart illustrates the current digital library projects and initiatives of participants

Quick Break

10:45 am Large Group Discussion: Challenges, Gaps, & Redundancies

Strategic R&D decisions are informed by the challenges, gaps and redundancies in current projects and activities. This discussion will help reveal the strategic choices that will move R&D efforts forward. Comments are recorded live on the wall chart

- 12:00 pm** **Lunch**
Break for lunch in the same room
- 1:30 pm** **Strategic Design Questions for R&D Collaborations**
Using the landscape wall chart as input, participants will work at tables of 8 people to identify strategic questions that need to be discussed by *this group* to move R&D activities forward. *The purpose is to use the expertise and experience of the group to develop deeper insight about collaborative R&D opportunities.*
- 2:15 pm** **World Café – Focused Discussions about Digital Library R&D**
Participants will discuss questions with the purpose of fleshing out the strategic importance of the issue, what projects address this issues now and with what success, necessary partners to succeed in addressing this issue, what is the range of approaches to solve the problem/address the issue, etc. There will be a template to help guide the conversation and record comments.
- 4:30 pm** **Conversation Highlights & Insights**
As a large group, share insights about possible collaborations, project ideas, potential/new R&D efforts. This is a way to harvest actionable ideas from the world café conversations
- 5:00 pm** **Day 1 Wrap Up**
Mike Keller and/or Chuck Henry offer concluding remarks
- 5:00 pm** **Shuttle to Sheraton Palo Alto Available**
5:45 pm **Shuttle departs Sheraton Palo Alto for Cantor Arts Center**
- 6:00 pm** **Reception & Dinner - Cantor Arts Center, Stanford University**
The shuttle will be available throughout the evening for transportation between Cantor and the Sheraton Palo Alto

Dec. 1st
Second Working Day

Bender Room, Green Library
Stanford University

- 8:20 & 8:40am** Shuttles depart Sheraton Palo Alto
- 8:30 am** **Breakfast buffet in Library**
- 9:00 am** **Welcome & Orientation**
Mike Keller and Chuck Henry welcome everyone back

- 9:15 am** **World Café – Deeper Discussions Continued**
During this morning we will do two more sessions of world café.
- 11:30 am** **Conversation Highlights & Insights**
As a large group, share insights about possible collaborations, project ideas, potential/new R&D efforts
- 12:00 pm** **Lunch**
- 1:30 pm** **“Rapid Prototyping” R&D Collaborations**
Participants will take their ideas of possible collaborations and new R&D efforts further by exploring what they might look like and how they might work by using concrete objects, drawing, mockups, etc. The purpose is not to come up with an actual model of a project, but to explore the opportunities and limitations of various ideas and gain more clarity about what it takes to make this collaboration/project work. This process will reveal opportunities and insights about collaboration that can be followed up on during the remainder of the meeting.
- 2:30 pm** **Gallery Walk – Touring the Prototypes**
Participants visit all the tables (8-10) to see, review the prototypes.
- 3:15 pm** **Large Group Discussion – Actions for Collaborating**
This final discussion will move the group toward articulating:
-specific collaborative projects that are possible/desirable
-levels of commitment, milestones
-potential partnerships (duos, trios)
- 4:30 pm** **Closing comments & Next Steps**
Mike Keller and/or Chuck Henry make closing remarks
- 5:00 pm** **Adjourn**
- 5:00 pm** **Shuttle to Sheraton Palo Alto available**
- 5:45 pm** **Shuttle departs Sheraton Palo Alto for Schwab Center**
- 6:00 pm** **Reception & Dinner - Schwab Center, Stanford University**
The shuttle will be available throughout the evening for transportation between the Schwab Center and the Sheraton Palo Alto